

Ways to use Educational Methods in Working with Teenagers

Sarsenbaeva Raikhon Makhanbetovna

Candidate of Pedagogical Sciences, acting as Associate Professor of the Department
of Pedagogy and Psychology at the ISFT Institute

Abstract: In particular, a teenager; upbringing; working with teenagers with difficult upbringing; adolescence is considered the main stage when the most important characteristics of a teenager are formed; teenagers with difficult studies violate school discipline and order; do not want to study; information is expressed about conflicts with teachers, peers, parents, etc.

Keywords: Comprehensive schools; work with teenagers, education, teenagers with learning difficulties; method; teaching methods; specific characteristics; violation of school discipline and order; unwillingness to study; teachers; peers; ways, means and forms of conflict between a teenager and his parents that affect students; good personal qualities; educational process; self-approval; self-criticism; self-encouragement; self-discipline.

Introduction. As you know, one of the main problems of secondary schools is the issue of working with difficult-to-educate teenagers, that is, boys and girls aged 11-16 years.

During this period, the process of personality formation is extremely important. At the same time, this period is a very difficult and difficult period for both teenagers and teachers.

“The 44th goal of the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On the development strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026” is defined as follows: To improve the quality of education in schools, to bring the knowledge and skills of teachers to the international level.

Determine local or international certification requirements for each subject to operate the school.

Diagnostics of the knowledge and skills of teachers in schools that do not have a category.

Continue to staff secondary schools, especially educational institutions in remote areas, with highly educated teaching staff.

Further improvement of the system for appointing a principal and his deputies in schools, taking into account the participation of school teachers and parents.

Optimization of the activities of district departments of the public education system through complete digitalization¹.”²

During adolescence, the child’s living conditions and activities are very changeable, that is, restructuring occurs in his psyche. New forms of treatment of equals begin to emerge. In the

¹ Optimization is the achievement of high results by spending less effort, less money and time in the pedagogical process.

² Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan DP No. 60 “On the development strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026.” January 28, 2022.

student community, changes are taking place in the social status of a teenager with a difficult upbringing; parents and teachers make various demands on him, and tests begin to be carried out.

At the age of 11-16, a teenager with a difficult upbringing begins to temporarily separate from family and school. In the formation of a teenager, the importance of parents decreases. Usually he is busy choosing between a formal group and an informal therapeutic group and, finally, chooses the group in which he feels comfortable and is treated with respect, that is, he considers the informal group to be preferable. Adolescence is the main stage during which the most important characteristics of a teenager are formed. This stage represents the period between childhood and adulthood. A teenager is not yet developed enough to consider himself an adult, but at the same time he is considered developed enough to interact with other people and follow the requirements of social norms and rules in his actions.

A teenager is not an adult. This is a person who is at the stage of forming the most important qualities and aspects of his personality. This stage represents the period between childhood and adulthood. A person is not yet developed enough to consider himself an adult, but at the same time he is developed enough to interact with other people and follow the requirements of social norms and rules in his actions.³

It is believed that a teenager is capable of making reasonable decisions, taking conscious actions and bearing moral and legal responsibility for them. It should be noted that the teenager is also a person who is legally responsible for his actions.⁴

Teenagers with difficult upbringings are physically healthy, but their upbringing, that is, their behavior, is disturbed. Teenagers with difficult upbringings lag behind their peers academically, especially well-educated teenagers, because they have underdeveloped abilities such as attention, memory, thinking and imagination.

We know that working with teenage students is a very complex pedagogical process. Therefore, it is not easy for teachers to work with students, especially teenagers. Teachers need to be very careful when working with teenagers. Because teenagers have one sentence less and two more, so they need to find one and a half sentences to speak out.

In turn, the professional activities of these specialists have a number of differences that make it possible to determine their specific characteristics. The teacher, fulfilling his main task of teaching, passes on to the younger generation the knowledge and experience of social culture acquired by society. In this process, the child is raised and formed.⁵

Working with teenagers with difficult upbringings involves a process of pedagogical re-education. Re-education refers to overcoming or eliminating various restrictions in the behavior and behavior of a teenager with learning difficulties. The process of re-education is a difficult process for social educators and adolescents with learning difficulties. Teenagers with difficult upbringings should be interested in their future lifestyle. A social educator must analyze the past and present of adolescents with difficult upbringings and imagine their future.⁶

Teenagers with difficult upbringings violate school discipline and order, do not want to study, and conflict with teachers, peers, and parents. They drop out of school, consider themselves

³ Egamberdieva N. Social pedagogy. Textbook. – T.: Publishing House of the National Library of Uzbekistan named after Alisher Navoi, 2009. – 234 p.

⁴ Khasanboeva N. Social pedagogy. Textbook. – T.: National Library of Uzbekistan named after Alisher Navoi, 2019.

⁵ Sarsenbaeva R.M. Methods of educational work. Study guide. – T.: “Finance-Economics”, 2019. – 388 p.

⁶ Sarsenbaeva R.M. Ways of training and re-education of adolescents with difficult upbringings. Volume: Miasto Przyszłości Kielce. 2024-09-02 /ISSN/2544-980X <https://miastoprzyszlosci.com.pl/index.php/mp/article/view/4627> Polish Journal WAK

unlucky, become babysitters, drink alcohol, take drugs and commit crimes. It is teenagers who may commit suicide as a result of physical or sexual violence.⁷

Teenagers react differently to one or another educational influence. This situation depends on their particular individual characteristics, level of upbringing and the extent to which the teacher used teaching methods, that is, how much he used them correctly, effectively or skillfully.⁸

Education⁹ as the main object of pedagogy has been the focus of attention of scientists throughout the entire history of the development of pedagogy. At the same time, the meaning of the concept of “education” has practical significance. Because this concept defines the main approaches to the tasks and goals of pedagogical activity.

Teachers who teach different subjects explore children's interests and involve them in various clubs and activities. The school hosts various educational events and competitions. When carrying out these events, they use the help of parents and former students, and invite famous people to the school. The main factor in the socialization of school-age children is the peer group, which forms a children's subculture¹⁰. A social teacher must know the functions of these phenomena and be able to see their place in the development of personal qualities and social relationships of students.¹¹

By education we mean the formation of personal and moral qualities in the person being formed. Being closely related to education, education also has its own laws. Education is a single process. But they are not exactly alike. The unity of education and training lies primarily in the commonality of their goals.¹²

⁷ Sarsenbaeva R.M. Ways of training and re-education of adolescents with difficult upbringings. Volume: Miasto Przyszłości Kielce. 2024-09-02 /ISSN/2544-980X <https://miastoprzyszlosci.com.pl/index.php/mp/article/view/4627> Polish Journal WAK

⁸ Egamberdieva N. Social pedagogy. Textbook. – T.: Publishing House of the National Library of Uzbekistan named after Alisher Navoi, 2009. – 234 p.

⁹ Education is a practical pedagogical process aimed at developing in a person certain physical, mental, moral and spiritual qualities.

¹⁰ **Subculture** (Latin sub - “bottom” and culture) is a term in sociology, anthropology and cultural studies, denoting a sharply differentiated part of the culture of a society. Within a subculture, there may be distinctive clothing, slang, behavior, and other cultural norms.

¹¹ R. M. Sarsenbaeva. Social and pedagogical activities with teenagers in secondary schools. Uzbekistan, WAK Journal. Contributions of eastern thinkers to natural sciences (Online scientific journal “Sustainable Development and Leading Research”). 2023, Volume 03, Issue 11.

¹² Sarsenbaeva R.M. Methods of educational work. Study guide. – T.: “Finance-Economics”, 2019. – 388 p.

<p style="text-align: center;">Educational tasks</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The educational method is the systematic educational influence of educators and teachers on students 	
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In pedagogy, educational methods¹³ mean a systematic influence on consciousness, emotions, will and a system of relationships with the goal of comprehensive personality formation. Educational methods are understood as methods, means and forms of influence of teacher educators on students, methods of pedagogical organization of the educational process with the aim of instilling in students the qualities of a comprehensively developed personality.

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Moreover, due to the versatility of the content of education, educational methods are considered diverse, and which one should be chosen and when to use them depends on the degree of ignorance committed by these adolescents. Of course, at some stage in the educational process, teaching methods may be used separately, and sometimes separately. The use of certain teaching methods depends on specific pedagogical conditions and the psychological and physiological characteristics of adolescent students.

<p style="text-align: center;">Methods of education</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - It depends on what teaching methods educators and teachers use, how they know how to apply them, on the culture of treatment and on how qualified they are in their profession 	
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¹³ **Method** (Greek "metodos" - way of knowledge or research, theory, teaching) - practical and theoretical mastery of reality, mastery, training, guidelines for knowledge, a set of methods, a method of creating and substantiating philosophical knowledge.

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In the entire pedagogical process, education always performs educational tasks, and education performs the responsible task of learning about life and preparing for it. The challenges of education are multifaceted. If the main purpose of education is to equip students with knowledge, then education plays an important role in shaping the beliefs, moral concepts and skills, needs and aspirations of young people who can respond to the laws of our society.¹⁵

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“According to Appendix 1 of the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. DP-158 dated September 11, 2023 “On the Strategy of Uzbekistan - 2030” in paragraph I of the performance indicators for achieving goals until 2030,” Every person must realize their potential. In section 1.1 “Education system reforms” “Improving the status of teaching staff, bringing their knowledge and qualifications in line with international standards” the following was defined:

- 1). Sending 1000 educators and teachers to foreign countries for training and internships.
- 2). Double the average salary of teachers in preschool educational organizations and secondary educational institutions.
- 3). Continuous training of 500,000 employees of preschool education organizations and general secondary education institutions.
- 4). Introduction of a training system in areas of teacher education for applicants in particularly needy areas and remote areas on the basis of a full state grant¹⁶.

Natural methods are determined by the goal of the comprehensive development of the student's personality and include many educational influences associated with the educational process.

¹⁵ Sarsenbaeva R.M. Methods of educational work. Study guide. – T.: “Finance-Economics”, 2019. – 388 p.

¹⁶ Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated September 11, 2023 No. DP-158 “On the strategy of Uzbekistan - 2030”.

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Problems in this regard are solved by educating the younger generation as an active and comprehensively developed individual working for the development of the country and the well-being of the people, and by involving them in this struggle. Based on this idea, in the process of education it is necessary to use teaching methods in accordance with its laws.

Educational methods are the ways in which teachers and other communities (parents, relatives, neighbors, neighbours) develop ideological and spiritual beliefs and spiritual feelings in students. We are talking about a pedagogical process that is used to find positive content in them and their habits and systematically has an educational effect on the personality of the student. Educational methods also include organizing work to improve the personality of teenage students. Education is a two-way pedagogical process that combines the activities of the teaching staff and the student body.

The correct choice of teaching methods contributes to a positive increase in the activity of self-education of adolescents in solving educational problems. For example, when working with adolescents, the teacher should emphasize their learning, behavior, adherence to rules of conduct, the importance of having a clear agenda, following a strict order, activities such as conversation, and learning through the effective use of explanatory methods. Also, along with conversational and explanatory methods, the teacher helps to develop in adolescents such human qualities as correctly entering the classroom, greeting the teacher and students, maintaining order and discipline.

General secondary (eleven years of education), specialized secondary (nine years of basic secondary and two years of secondary specialized education), primary vocational education (complete persons who have received nine years of basic secondary and two years of primary vocational education), as well as secondary specialized and vocational education (nine-year general secondary and three-year persons who have received secondary specialized, vocational education) have the right to receive higher education.¹⁷

At the same time, highly educated teachers warn teenagers about the above processes during classes. In this process, it is necessary to encourage teenage students who actively participate in positive work, educational work, sports and educational events. The teacher must approve, praise, morally or financially encourage teenagers when they complete tasks correctly, when they did not complete tasks, were inattentive, did not work, did not finish work, were irresponsible, and used methods of reprimanding teenagers.

¹⁷ Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Education". LRU-637 No. 09/23/2020.

In pedagogy, a number of teaching methods are studied, including the following:¹⁸

- methods that serve to form public consciousness;
- methods of habituation and learning activities;
- methods of encouragement and punishment in education;
- methods of narration, explanation, teaching, lecture, moral (spiritual) conversation and discussion;
- methods of motivation: approval, encouragement, assurance, recording, verbal or written gratitude, methods of moral or material reward;
- methods of punishment: statement, threat (intimidation), prohibition, reprimand, embarrassment (blushing), fight, discussion in a group, denunciation, prohibition, lowering of reputation;
- pedagogical requirements, training, educational tasks, competitions, public opinion and exemplary methods.

Self-motivation and self-control play an important role in self-discipline and self-correction. Examples of this include self-encouragement and approval. “That’s right, well done, keep up the good work,” he encourages the teenager, instilling in him the desire to be more successful. Self-approval should be distinguished from self-love, which arises as a result of an uncritical look at the results of one’s activities. Self-approval occurs along with self-criticism.

¹⁸ Ataeva N., Rasulova F., Gasanov S. General pedagogy (fundamentals of theory and practice of pedagogy). Study guide. - T.: “Science and Technology”, 2012, 936 p.

The process of preparing for self-education consists of several stages:

1. Study yourself, collect your positive and negative moral qualities and character;
2. Systematically manipulate your mind to change your behavior;
3. Get out of the crisis and focus on self-education.

Re-education of a teenager is a purposeful, planned re-education of students with educational deficiencies. Re-education of a teenager is a practical activity that shows the fallacy of the concepts and methods of difficult youth and makes them think about their behavior.

In the initial period of self-education, it is used to test one's strengths and abilities, and is also associated with a person's self-knowledge. For example, teenagers who are participants in sports, cultural or intellectual clubs, amateur clubs and various scientific clubs, when they have difficulty completing exercises and tasks in the work they have started, even if they do not work or are not able to complete the work and tasks they have started, they encourage yourself with the words "This is not bad, it should be good!", "It's much better now, try a little more". Self-encouragement is especially effective when each person seeks out positive role models. If he is demanding of himself and follows the motto "If others can do it, then I can do it," he will achieve his goal.

Self-encouragement should be distinguished from self-confidence, arrogance and boasting. Sometimes some teenagers boast: "What if I want, I can do it myself." However, they do not understand that in order to perform this or that action, they need to know it and have the skills.

Self-encouragement comes with self-reflection. Self-motivation will be more effective when every teenager has a correct and clear idea of himself, his strengths and abilities.

Self-education is a pedagogical activity aimed at changing a person in accordance with consciously defined goals, established procedures, ideas and beliefs. Self-discipline presupposes a certain level of personality development, self-awareness and its analysis, while consciously comparing one's actions with the actions of other people.

Conclusion. In conclusion, teacher educators should be very careful when working with adolescents. In addition, teacher educators must use teaching methods effectively and efficiently and consciously anticipate the possibility of positive situations arising as a result. If on the contrary, then this situation can have a negative impact on adolescents. At the same time, their faith in life, in people, in a word, in society is lost.

REFERENCES

1. Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Education". LRU-637 No. 09/23/2020.
2. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated September 11, 2023 No. DP-158 "On the strategy of Uzbekistan - 2030".

3. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan DP No. 60 “On the development strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026.” January 28, 2022.
4. Ataeva N., Rasulova F., Gasanov S. General pedagogy (Fundamentals of theory and practice of pedagogy). Study guide. - T.: “Science and Technology”, 2012, 936 p.
5. Egamberdieva N. Social pedagogy. Textbook. – T.: Publishing House of the National Library of Uzbekistan named after Alisher Navoi, 2009. – 234 p.
6. Sarsenbaeva R.M. Methods of educational work. Study guide. – T.: “Finance-Economics”, 2019. – 388 p.
7. Sarsenbaeva R.M. Social and pedagogical activities with teenagers in secondary schools. Uzbekistan, WAK Journal. Contributions of eastern thinkers to natural sciences (Online scientific journal “Sustainable Development and Leading Research”). 2023, Volume 03, Issue 11.
8. Sarsenbaeva R.M. Ways of training and re-education of adolescents with difficult upbringings. Volume: Miasto Przyszłości Kielce. 2024-09-02 /ISSN/2544-980X <https://miastoprzyszlosci.com.pl/index.php/mp/article/view/4627>, Polish Journal WAK
9. Khasanboeva N. Social pedagogy. Textbook. – T.: National Library of Uzbekistan named after Alisher Navoi, 2019.